

FPGA-Based RF Spectrum Merging and Adaptive Hopset Selection

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Abstract—The radio frequency (RF) spectrum is a limited resource. Spectrum allotment disputes stem from this scarcity as many radio devices are confined to a fixed frequency or frequency sequence. One alternative is to incorporate cognition within a reconfigurable radio platform, therefore enabling the radio to adapt to dynamic RF spectrum environments. In this way, the radio is able to actively sense the RF spectrum, decide, and act accordingly, thereby sharing the spectrum and operating in more flexible manner. In this paper, we present a novel solution for merging many distributed RF spectrum maps into one map and for subsequently creating an adaptive hopset. We also provide an example of our system in operation, the result of which is a pseudorandom adaptive hopset. The paper then presents a novel hardware design for the frequency merger and adaptive hopset selector, both of which are written in VHDL and implemented as a custom IP core on an FPGA-based embedded system using the Xilinx Embedded Development Kit (EDK) software tool. The design of the custom IP core is optimized for area, and it can process a high-volume digital input via a low-latency circuit architecture. The complete embedded system includes the Xilinx PowerPC microprocessor, UART serial connection, and compact flash memory card IP cores, and our custom map merging/hopset selection IP core, all of which are targeted to the Virtex IV FPGA. This system is then incorporated into a cognitive radio prototype on a Rice University Wireless Open Access Research Platform (WARP) reconfigurable radio.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Today's radio environment is congested. Within the United States (US), the current paradigm hinges on the fixed frequency assignment and licensure to millions of radio users through Federal Communications Commission (FCC). For the assignment scheme to work, users must be packed tightly within adjacent bands. Likewise, for the users' radios to coexist in harmony, their radios must adhere to strict

radio frequency (RF) masks to prevent leakage of energy into adjacent bands and cause interference to other nearby licensed users. These issues could be mitigated or solved if RF devices were adaptable to spectrum usage. An FPGA presents a desirable solution given the its compact circuitry and reconfigurable nature.

The Cognitive Radio

Cognitive communication technology enables the development of adaptive systems. A cognitive radio network allows a group of cognitive radio (CR) devices to effectively communicate in a manner which eliminates interference to other radios or radio networks. Implementing adaptive frequency hopping (AFH) in such a network provides additional interference resistance. This paper demonstrates the feasibility of using a field programmable gate array (FPGA) to merge spectrum observations from multiple network nodes and create an adaptive hopset for use in AFH operation.

Cognitive radio operation, or the cognitive process, closely follows that of the *observe-orient-decide-act* (OODA) loop made famous by military strategist Colonel John Boyd. First, the radio observes its surroundings by sensing the neighboring RF spectrum. Next, it orients itself to its surroundings by combining the spectrum sensor data into a usable spectrum map and identifying available spectrum resources. The radio then uses the RF spectrum availability map to decide on a specific means of transmission (i.e. frequency, frequency-hopping sequence, waveform type, etc.). Lastly, the radio acts by transmitting and/or receiving according to its decision. A CR network consists of one or more CRs existing in this fashion [1].

Frequency hopping is a means of switching between radio frequencies for any number of purposes. The most obvious is the avoidance of RF interference sources. Whereas current frequency hopping techniques use a fixed hopset, adaptive hopsets are formed according to current spectrum usage. By extension, an AFH CR network consists of two or more CRs communicating in this fashion.

The FPGA as a CR Platform

FPGAs represent a unique blend of hardware speed and compactness with the ability to be rapidly prototyped and reconfigured similar to software. By combining these traits, we can formulate a system which allows us to process large

Figure 1 – System functional diagram. This paper demonstrates the two steps colored red.

datasets (i.e., RF spectrum maps) on a circuit level. Implementing this design strictly in software on a general purpose processor (GPP) would require less development overhead, but the merging operation would take perhaps an order of magnitude more clock cycles to complete as software instructions take considerably more clock cycles than hardware operations. An application-specific (ASIC) design allows for extremely fast computations, but the development lifecycle is well beyond the time and resources of this project. A graphics processing unit (GPU) would be an acceptable alternative due to the inherent parallelization and high speed characteristics, but we have selected a radio development platform on which an FPGA is the computational centerpiece. Therefore, an FPGA best suits our design needs.

While this research is part of a larger effort, this paper focuses exclusively on leveraging an FPGA’s speed and flexibility in fusing nodes’ spectrum maps into a common map containing information about the availability of each frequency. This common map, in turn, forms the basis for selecting an adaptive hopset for the network. Eventually, this research will support the broader goal of enabling dynamic adaptive hopset selection in an AFH CR network.

Whole System Structure

The spectrum merger and hopset selector research detailed in this paper is part of a larger system architecture whose functionality is modeled by a state machine in Figure 1. As stated previously, the system functions in a cognitive manner, i.e. by observation, orientation, decision, and action. First, the spectrum is observed through some sensing

mechanism. If the spectrum is unchanged, the system continues to observe the spectrum. Otherwise, the spectrum is parsed into a REM which is intelligible by the rest of the network. After REMs are exchanged, the network is clustered into subnets based on physical proximity and REM similarity. Once the network has been partitioned into subnets, the hardware creates an aggregate map and generates an adaptive hopset based on that map. If the new hopset is not the same as its predecessor, the new hopset is distributed. The new hopset is used and the system resumes sensing as this process is repeated forever. The two states demonstrated in this paper are colored red in Figure 1.

2. BACKGROUND

Spectrum Mapping

An RF spectrum can be represented in many different ways, such as real+complex number pairs, a histogram-like FFT model, and so forth. Prior to conducting this experiment, it is necessary to choose a method such that it is both portable between components and extensible for future research. One method generalizes the RF spectrum as part of a larger set of data, the radio environment. In their pioneering Radio Environment Map (REM) research, Zhao, Le, and Reed present the RF spectrum as part of a larger model containing multiple quantitative and qualitative radio environment characteristics to include terrain, historical or time-based usage data, and others in addition to the obvious inclusion of present RF spectrum usage [1].

This paper implements the REM solely as an avenue for storing spectrum availability data. Our REM implementation stores channel-specific data as a binary vector so as to aid in the fast determination of a common map. This concept is validated in section three. Therefore, and for the rest of this paper, the spectrum map is referred to simply as the REM to allow for expansion of this research to include more aspects of the radio environment.

Bluetooth (802.15.1) and WLAN (802.11)

Adaptive frequency hopping is an emerging trend in CR networks. As they are already able to sense spectrum availability, CR networks are natural candidates for expanding the adaptive envelope to include entire hopsets in addition to single frequencies. An example of AFH in practice is the current Bluetooth implementation. Whereas the early standard was spread out across 79 of the possible 83.5 ISM channels, Bluetooth AFH versions need only hop over 15 channels. This allows for much less interference to other devices operating in the same band, including WLAN (802.11) and ZigBee (802.15.4) [2-3].

Dynamic Adaptive Frequency Hopping

The authors of [4] propose the dynamic adaptive frequency hopping (DAFH) algorithm in wireless personal area networks (WPANs). They define DAFH as a general method that enables the FH-networks in the unlicensed band to avoid mutual interference in a distributed manner. Their

approach is similar to ours in that they determine available frequencies and select a hopset using a common seed for pseudorandom hopset generation. The authors also implement per-subnet band division, i.e. the overall band is partitioned such that every neighboring subnet uses a separate frequency sample space to avoid collisions between hopsets. We currently intend to simply ensure no two subnets will share the same hop at the same time, but the technique in [4] is certainly worthwhile to explore for future development.

FPGA-Based Cognitive Radio

KUAR: Kansas University Agile Radio—The University of Kansas uses a Virtex-II Pro FPGA for the digital signal processing operations and digital communication components of their software-defined radio platform KUAR. It performs communications processing in VHDL on the FPGA, does signal processing, radio control, and RF environment sensing with both VHDL on the FPGA and C code on the FPGAs embedded processor, and interfaces with a transceiver and a Linux control processor [5].

WARP: Wireless Open-Access Research Platform—Rice University uses the PowerPC processor on the Virtex-II Pro FPGA for communication processing on their Wireless Open-Access Research Platform. WARP is used to prototype wireless networks. They have tested and verified the FPGAs on the WARP board in over-the-air tests. The single-input single-output (SISO) Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) transceiver uses the FPGA for all the baseband processing. It uses the radio daughtercards on the WARP board to convert to the RF band [6].

Trinity Colleges Cognitive Radio Framework—The authors of [7] at Trinity College performed a case study that demonstrated the implementation of cognitive radio on an FPGA. They created a set of tools for radio designers to be able to implement cognitive radio on FPGAs. This research used a partial reconfiguration of the FPGAs during runtime, allowing a cognitive engine to reconfigure both the software and hardware.

Our Contribution—Our work is novel in three ways. First, we use an FPGA to implement a cognitive radio and implement an adaptive hopset. Like those in the previous work, we leverage the FPGA features of flexibility and compact area for our advantage. We use the base WARP system, a custom IP core written in VHDL, and the Virtex IV’s embedded PowerPC core with C code to implement the radio and hopset selector. By designing our implementation around the WARP architecture, we also contribute to the working body of knowledge on WARP-centric cognitive radio projects. Finally, we demonstrate a novel method for generating a random adaptive hopset for a frequency-hopping cognitive radio.

3. METHODOLOGY

Spectrum Input

Spectrum sensing is the first step in forming the adaptive hopset. First, a radio front-end receiver (Rx) senses the spectrum. An analog-to-digital (ADC) converter converts this signal to its digital equivalent. Next, a Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is performed on the digitized signal to generate an N-bin frequency-domain model of the signal. The spectrum parsing component converts each bin to a binary ‘1’ or ‘0’ (e.g., ‘1’ if the spectrum is unused above the receivers predetermined noise threshold, otherwise ‘0’). Additionally, the number of bins that corresponds to one discrete channel depends on the channel bandwidth required by the user. We assume that the mapping of bins to channels and/or center frequencies has already been established. The result of this process is an N-bit binary vector model of the spectrum where ones represent available frequencies and zeros show unavailable spectrum. This is how we choose to implement the REM. This process is shown in Figure 2.

The portion of Figure 2 in dashed lines shows the REM distribution process and the centralized REM-based network clustering process. Once clusters exist, common REMs can be formed for individual clusters and the network as a whole using the same merging process. Clustering is not a focus of this paper, however, and will not be explained further here.

Figure 2 – Spectrum input diagram. Components designed for this experiment are shown as shaded.

Figure 3– AHS structural diagram. Buses are shown in bold, and bus widths are in square brackets.

Figure 4 – FPGA bus structure diagram.

In this paper, we assume spectrum sensing is complete for the network, that every node can represent its REM in this manner, and that all nodes have received the REMs of all nodes in the network. In terms of Figure 2, we assume that all steps prior to the REM Merger block are complete and REM vectors are ready for merging.

Figure 5– Example bandwidth mask vector.

FPGA Internal Structure

We implement our design on a Xilinx Virtex IV FPGA as part of the WARP II radio transceiver board. Using the Xilinx Embedded Development Kit (EDK), we assemble a collection of custom and existing intellectual property (IP) cores using a 32-bit bus and the FPGA’s embedded PowerPC processor. In Figure 4, green cores are affiliated with the PowerPC, blue cores are WARP-specific, tan cores are those needed to support our IP core, and our core is shown in red. Cores with an asterisk (*) are not used in this experiment, but will be used in future development.

The IP cores supporting our core are RS-232 (for output to PC serial port terminal) and a removable CompactFlash memory. The latter two IP cores are grouped together by a gray dashed line because they are interchangeable as method for exchanging REMs. Initially, we simply write each node’s REM to the removable memory and transfer REMs between nodes in this fashion. Future iterations of this design include transmit REM data via wired network for system testing purposes. Finally, radios will operate in a completely wireless fashion using their radio cards. The bus structure of our design is shown in Figure 4.

IP Core Internal Structure

Our IP core consists of six components: REM merger, key loader, two 64x32 register files for storing the aggregate REM and the key, the hopset selector, and a BRAM section

in which open channels are stored. Their organization is shown in Figure 3.

IP Core Internal Function

Bandwidth Masking—Different radio protocols have different bandwidth requirements. In order to provide flexibility with regard to these requirements, our device accepts two 32-bit bandwidth masks. When the hardware scans the aggregate REM for available channels, the two masks are applied to determine whether the required band is available. For example, if a given protocol requires B bins to be available around a center frequency, the user specifies the corresponding bits in the bandwidth mask input vectors as ‘high’. The construction of the bandwidth mask is shown in Figure 5.

REM Merging Components—REM merging is the first core function of this design. On a high level, REM merging is the process of successive bitwise AND operations. In this manner, the AND of any number of REMs produces a new REM for which available channels are the intersection of all available channels across all input REMs. In this paper, we assume $N = 2048$ such that each REM is a 2048-bit binary vector, the direct result of a 2048-bin FFT. We also assume the maximum network size is $N = 64$ nodes. Each vector is loaded successively and ANDed with the previous result. There is no physical limit to the number of input REMs, although the number of possible REMs is ultimately limited to the network size. All vectors are serially loaded at a rate of one word per clock cycle. The number of clock cycles needed to load a map is modeled by Equation 1.

$$cycles = \#REM \times \frac{N \text{ bits}}{REM} \times \frac{1 \text{ cycle}}{Buswidth} \quad (1)$$

For example, consider the scenario in which 64 REMs are used. Therefore, for 128-bit maps with a 32-bit bus, it will take

$$64 \text{ REMs} \times \frac{128 \text{ bits}}{REM} \times \frac{1 \text{ cycle}}{32 \text{ bits}} = 256 \text{ cycles}$$

to load a map. If the number of vectors is less than the total number of possible input gates, unused input gates are assigned all ones such that the bitwise AND of any vector with that of all ones results in the original vector. All vectors are serially loaded at a rate of one word per clock cycle.

The REM merger can accept an arbitrary number of maps as the hardware component logically ANDs each 32-bit input with its respective section in the aggregate REM. For example, if the n^{th} 32-bit section of a REM is loaded into the REM merger, it will be ANDed with the n^{th} section of the REM stored by the merger. The result is then written to the register storing that section of the aggregate REM. In this way, any number of devices in a network can share REMs for the purpose of creating an adaptive hopset.

Adaptive Hopset Selection—Adaptive hopset selection, or AHS, represents the second core function of our design. Map merging generates the aggregate REM as a binary vector in which each bit maps to the center frequency of an FFT bin within the device’s usable spectrum. Because all radios within the network know this mapping, adaptive hopset selection becomes a matter of randomizing these channels. We assume the hopset is H hops in length, bit position-to-channel mappings are stored in the device (i.e., in a look-up table), and an N-bit cryptographically-random number R exists prior to forming the hopset. Under these assumptions, our circuit performs the following steps on an N-bit REM to convert the map into a corresponding adaptive hopset:

- (1) Starting at the lowest-number channel, begin iterating through the binary vector. Initialize the available channel count $C = 0$.
- (2) For every bit, if the bit is a ‘1’, look up the corresponding channel number and store it in a list L containing available channels and increment C.
- (3) If $C < H$, replicate the first $H-C$ at the end of the list L such that L has H elements.
- (4) For $i = 0$ to $i = H-1$, look up the available channel in L at the index indicated by the key K, scaled to the number of open channels. Output the channel in L as the i -th hop in hopset S. Rotate K one bit to the right.
- (5) Repeat step four H times, i.e., until all H hops have been assigned within S.

The hopset S of length N is this system’s output. Because

Figure 6 – AHS functional diagram.

each index is derived from a random number, every index is therefore also random. This process is graphically summarized in Figure 6.

System Testing

VHDL code was developed in ModelSim PE. Once we developed a consistent simulation design, we synthesized the hopset selector core in the Xilinx ISE implementation tool. We used the mapped version of the circuit to confirm the design’s functionality with the effects of realistic delays and other hardware characteristics prior to loading the integrating the circuit with the rest of the WARP system. We show the results of this simulation in section four.

We tested the hardware system using C code implemented on the FPGA’s embedded processor core by reading in the spectrum maps from a compact flash file, submitting the maps to the VHDL code described above, and writing the resulting hopset(s) to a new compact flash file to simulate REM reception and hopset transmission over the network. We use random maps and a random key to ensure a random hopset is indeed generated from a realistic input.

Optimization Goals

Virtex IV FPGA resources are already limited, and incorporating the existing WARP system causes the design to be even more crowded. Therefore, this design is optimized for area. Because the state machines and other logic in our IP core require relatively little area (on the order of 5% total resources), our primary optimization was to minimize the effort needed to synthesize and implement memory. This strategy implicitly attempts to use memory components built into the board. We used a generic VHDL block RAM (BRAM) structure given in the XST User Guide for storing available channels. BRAM usage is shown in Figure 13 as the blue lines within the pink columns.

4. RESULTS

Mapped Simulation

In order to validate our design before running the time-intensive place-and-route process and to facilitate quicker debugging, we simulated the synthesized/mapped version of our circuit. Figures 7-12 detail this simulation and reinforce our assertion that the circuit performs as intended given realistic hardware constraints. Signals of interest are described in captions and highlighted in red boxes. The synthesized component was instantiated in the same VHDL test bench used to evaluate our code base. Xilinx automatically generated the VHDL file using Unisim components which accurately model hardware constraints in simulation.

Standalone Device Usage

When placed and routed, the AHS (including a bus communication wrapper) occupies approximately 10% of the board’s slice resources. Because BRAM is used, the associated slice usage is limited to a small footprint. Two

BRAMs out of 376 total units are used to create the open channels table. Table 1 provides the device usage summaries for both the individual IP core (AHS) and the WARP-based system as a whole (AHS+WARP).

Figure 7 – Initially, the new_rems and new_key flags are toggled to clear the existing aggregate REM and key. The REMs are loaded by writing the 32 bits of REM data and toggling the load_key flag.

Figure 8 – The key is loaded in a similar fashion to the REM(s) with the load_key flag being toggled.

Figure 9 – Once the software has loaded the REMs and key, it toggles the start flag. The circuit immediately begins counting and tracking the open channels by first deasserting the finished flag. Hop channels are produced, but not read by the software.

Figure 10 – After the open channels have been counted, the hopset_ready flag is asserted. The software then toggles the next_hop flag in order to retrieve the hopset contents.

Figure 11 – The finished flag is asserted after all hops have been extracted. The hopset_ready flag is deasserted.

Figure 12 – Full system simulation. Hopset output occupies the most time because its speed is governed by that of the software running on the processor.

Table 1. Device Resource Usage Summary

Resource	Available	AHS	AHS+WARP
Number of BUFs	32	1 (3%)	11 (34%)
Number of External IOBs	768	256 (33%)	462 (69%)
Number of RAMB16s	376	2 (1%)	59 (15%)
Number of Slices Used	42,176	4,614 (10%)	15,032 (35%)
Number of SLICEMs	21,088	768 (3%)	1,119 (5%)

Timing Analysis

While the maximum frequency given by XST is only 70.442 MHz, the actual system can be run at a much higher frequency because of the automatic placement of clock dividers around the chip. For example, we run the PowerPC clock at 125 MHz and the bus clock at 100 MHz with no adverse effects. This is because the relatively low frequency applies only to a subset of clock nets.

Device Usage Floorplans

The PlanAhead diagram in Figure 13 shows how the slices (light blue) fill the FPGA fabric with our IP core alone and our IP core on top of the existing WARP system, respectively.

Optimization Achievements

Directing the synthesis and implementation tools to build the memory structure out of logic slices ran and did not complete, even when given over 12 hours to run. Purposefully using BRAM and using the XST option for automatically extracting BRAM was quick and resulted in virtually no synthesis and implementation overhead.

5. CONCLUSION

This research makes three novel contributions to the field of cognitive radio. First, we implement a cognitive radio with adaptive hopset selection on an FPGA. Second, we contribute to the overall WARP project repository. Finally, we demonstrate a novel hopset selection technique. The whole system comprising the WARP architecture and our custom core fits within the resources available to the Virtex IV FPGA. Because our code simulation, mapped hardware simulation, and software-based testing yield the same desired results, we conclude that this system functions as intended.

6. FUTURE WORK

This work composes the central component of the author’s master’s thesis. Additional research includes integrating the radio transceiver cards as the means of inter-device

Figure 13– AHS+WARP system device usage diagram.

communication, implementing network clustering, and establishing ordered communication within the network.

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BIOGRAPHIES

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